

Part II: Guidelines for Inclusive Support to Erasmus+ Students Across the Mobility Cycle

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This guideline is aimed to support understanding the roles and responsibilities of key HEI actors during the phases of the international student lifecycle. The guidelines are designed based on findings of four study visits conducted at four DiEM university partners, where individual interviews with key roles in mobility management and support for students were interviewed. Based on these study visits, the key roles for inclusive mobility support were narrowed down to five, including international relations office staff responsible for management of incoming and outgoing mobility, faculty/departmental coordinators, accessibility centres and student organisations.

To help distinguish the different stages of when the specific roles should act, the guideline follows the adapted international student lifecycle (Gabriels, W., Perez-Encinas, A. & Kotkiewicz, G. (2025) which includes the following phases:

1. **Pre-arrival:** The preparation phase in which students are equipped for their mobility experience. Support is aimed at providing practical information, briefings and language preparations
2. **On arrival:** The student transitions to a new academic and cultural environment.
3. **During the stay:** The student engages with the host HEI and with the sending institution. Support typically revolves around mentoring, integration activities, and language courses.
4. **Re-entry:** The support given to students as they reflect on their mobility experience and are back in their home country. This includes helping students readjusting to their home institutions and recognition of the skills and experiences they have had whilst on Erasmus+ exchange.

At the end of these guidelines, a roadmap towards inclusive mobility support is presented. The roadmap visualises the stages of mobility and the interventions that each key actor is expected to make in aspiration to create an inclusive environment at their institution for both incoming and outgoing mobility students.

Pre-Arrival Stage of Mobility

Pre-Arrival Stage of Mobility

For staff and organisations supporting Erasmus+ mobility, the preparation phase is essential for setting expectations and ensuring that all students, including those with fewer opportunities, are informed and equipped for their mobility experience. In this stage the main aims revolve around providing practical information, pre-departure briefings, and language preparation to outgoing students. Linked to these support mechanisms are the orientation meetings, access to student networks, and assessing the psychological readiness for cultural adaptation. These can make a significant difference for all students but especially to those with fewer opportunities who may need additional help. While previous research has shown that there are inconsistent support mechanisms within Erasmus+ countries, it is the pre-arrival stage that can help students with fewer opportunities the most, with explaining the financial support and finding a HEI that suits their needs. In this section the specific roles for Faculty coordinators, International Relations officer for incoming and outgoing departments, accessibility centres and student organisations, are discussed.

Faculty Coordinators

Information provision about mobility opportunities

Faculty Coordinators for Erasmus+ play a key role in informing students about mobility opportunities by combining structured communication channels with personalised guidance.

They should organise dedicated information sessions - online and on campus - to explain the Erasmus+ programme and answer students' academic or practical questions.

Faculty websites and university systems (email, social media, student platforms) should be used to share programme details, application procedures, and administrative requirements. Faculties ought to increasingly use student associations and student ambassadors to help disseminate information through their own networks.

Faculty coordinators are encouraged to have regular meetings with faculty and central leadership to ensure proper alignment of goals and tasks. While general information is often delivered centrally, Faculty Coordinators should offer tailored advice based on the faculty level realities, drawing on their subject-specific knowledge

	<p>and proximity to students to support informed decision-making at the central level of the HEI.</p>
Information on Financial questions	<p>Faculty Coordinators should have a supportive role in providing information about funding for student mobility. While the primary responsibility for financial aid details lies with the central International Relations/Mobility Office, coordinators should direct students to the appropriate contacts or offices.</p> <p>Faculty coordinators are encouraged to provide additional clarifications, especially when students need help navigating complex application requirements regarding financial support that students, including those with fewer opportunities may request.</p> <p>This task of Faculty coordinators should be as a supplementary role, it should overall consist in offering initial direction and support rather than detailed financial counselling.</p>
Curriculum related questions	<p>Faculty Coordinators are expected to play a facilitative role in guiding students toward the right sources of information about available courses.</p> <p>Regarding the Learning Agreement, Faculty coordinators should either refer to programme directors for detailed academic advice on course selections or themselves be involved in guiding students through the process.</p> <p>To support incoming students with their Learning Agreement, Faculty Coordinators should dedicate time to answering incoming students' emails regarding course-related questions.</p> <p>Faculty Coordinators that also teach, should provide more hands-on guidance, drawing on their subject-matter expertise to offer tailored advice on course compatibility and academic planning. In contrast, non-teaching coordinators should focus more on directing students to the appropriate academic contacts.</p>
Support in choosing mobility destination	<p>Faculty Coordinators should actively support students, including those with fewer opportunities in selecting appropriate mobility destinations, particularly by helping match students' academic profiles and interests with available partner universities. In the case of students with learning or physical disabilities, the Faculty</p>

	<p>coordinators should support the students in helping find the destination that best accommodates their needs.</p>
Support with the application process and Learning Agreement	<p>Preparation: Faculty Coordinators should provide students with guidance on the application process and requirements, though their level of involvement may vary depending on how centralised the process is at their institution.</p> <p>In universities where the student recruitment for going on Erasmus+ is centralised, the coordinator's role may be limited to promotion and individual consultations, with little influence over selection outcomes.</p> <p>In contrast, where faculties manage their own selection, coordinators should play a more active role, evaluating students based on a combination of grades, extracurricular activities, and scientific engagement. Their goals include assigning students to preferred destinations fairly while also considering institutional priorities.</p> <p>Learning Agreement: Faculty Coordinators should be actively involved in supporting students with the preparation and approval of the Learning Agreement. Their responsibilities are encouraged to include manually checking the Learning Agreement and verifying language certificates. They should ensure that the proposed curriculum aligns with faculty requirements and will be recognised upon the student's return by carefully reviewing the syllabus.</p>
Information about support available at host institution	<p>Faculty coordinators should facilitate the flow of information and communicate with other partners (hosting HEIs) on questions that may come from students.</p> <p>Faculty Coordinators are encouraged to refer to testimonials or collect first-hand information through surveys to outgoing students about the support students may receive at specific HEIs.</p> <p>Faculty Coordinators should build professional networks with partner institutions and between faculties. This will help them increase the quality and timing of the support of the information they seek.</p>

	<p>HEIs should support the development of professional networks through staff exchanges, staff weeks, and directly involving faculty coordinators in contacting the inter-institutional agreements.</p>
Information on Housing	<p>The Faculty Coordinator should inform students to contact the outgoing IRO officer regarding housing issues. For students with disabilities, they should encourage them to mention it directly to the IRO that provisions for their case should be made.</p>
Information about students with fewer opportunities	<p>Faculty Coordinators play a key role in liaising with accessibility and student services centres, which provide specialised guidance and support in cases involving students with fewer opportunities.</p> <p>In case they have special learning needs or other circumstances that require tailored support. It is advisable that faculty coordinators cooperate with the students, and if students disclose such information at the application stage, this should impact their choice of mobility destination. It is advisable that the faculty coordinators support students in obtaining information from partner institutions about available support at the receiving institution, especially when students are concerned about their needs being accommodated during mobility.</p>
Peer support	<p>Faculty Coordinators should facilitate connections between outgoing students and alumni who have previously studied at the same destination.</p> <p>To enhance early integration, Faculty Coordinators are encouraged to set-up mentoring programmes before the start of the mobility organised at the faculty level between incoming and local students.</p> <p>While faculties do not always manage formal buddy systems, coordinators are encouraged to promote existing initiatives like the ESN buddy system.</p> <p>Overall, coordinators should play a supportive role in encouraging peer-to-peer networks that help incoming and outgoing students feel connected and supported.</p>

International Relations Office (Outgoing Mobility)

<p>Informational provision about mobility opportunities</p>	<p>IROs play a crucial role in the promotion of mobility opportunities to students, especially at the central university level. Their responsibilities include organising information sessions for students each semester, providing guidance in open hour individual meetings or phone-based support. They are also encouraged to maintain up-to-date online resources, including detailed application instructions and programme information.</p> <p>IROs should also participate in peer-to-peer promotional activities such as by collaborating with the ESN local sections and other student organisations. It is advisable to include student testimonials and lived experiences in hybrid events with local student populations, and IROs should participate in central university promotional events and open days.</p> <p>IROs should support these efforts by using printed materials like flyers during face-to-face events and through digital media. Information that is relayed back to students should be done as inclusively as possible. For this, the manual on inclusive communication can help IROs in this endeavour.</p> <p>While the IRO coordinates the overarching promotion, they rely on partnerships with faculty coordinators and mobility alumni organisations, such as ESN, to enhance outreach and provide a richer picture of the mobility experience.</p> <p>Central IROs should also dedicate some time to the promotion of exchange possibilities to students with fewer opportunities and should include the different ways HEIs can support specific students with fewer opportunities.</p> <p>To ensure that all students receive the information about available help, we encourage IRO's staff to target all students but also to coordinate with services where students with fewer opportunities already go.</p>
<p>Information on financial questions</p>	<p>Information about funding availability is the most significant factor for students when they consider participation in mobility. IROs have a crucial task in communicating the eligibility criteria to students either directly or through using dissemination efforts such as</p>

	<p>events, student ambassadors, emails, etc.</p> <p>In a second step, IROs should provide guidance on the documentation required to prove eligibility through for instance open hours and ensure that students understand the process. Hence they should support students in preparing the necessary documentation.</p>
Information about available courses	<p>Before the mobility is approved, the IRO should enforce the link between students and faculty coordinators for the preparation of the Learning Agreement, explaining the rules, requirements and importantly, emphasise deadlines that need to be respected. This has to happen after the students are approved for mobility.</p> <p>This stage is an important stage for IROs as good selection of courses and mobility destination ensures the quality of the mobility.</p>
Support in choosing mobility destination	<p>The IRO plays a limited role in directly supporting students in choosing their mobility destination. However, IROs should play an important role in providing updated lists with institutional agreements and destinations in the case applications are centralised.</p>
Application support	<p>Application support may vary on the degree to which it is faculty coordinators support students in this phase. Once a student is nominated to go on mobility, IROs are recommended to hold info sessions or opening hours so that students may contact them. Most questions at this stage would revolve around administrative documentation, academic questions which should be left to the faculty coordinators and support at the host HEI.</p> <p>For Erasmus+ traineeships students, IROs have in many cases a bigger role to play in this process. They should inform those students on the eligibility criteria, support them through the application process such as through doing mock training interviews, and manage the applications. Establishing a relationship with the employer is also highly beneficial, especially for having the fastest information that can be provided to the student.</p>

Funding support information for students with fewer opportunities	<p>IRO staff responsible for outgoing mobility must inform the local student population of detailed eligibility criteria for additional funding support upon request. However, to increase the share of students with fewer opportunities that participate in the mobility programmes, it is highly advised to send this information with the general information about mobility support.</p> <p>IRO staff should receive from students proof that they are with fewer opportunities before providing the additional financial support. This can entail government-issued documents or income statements or proving a physical or learning disability.</p>
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International Relations Office (Incoming Mobility)

Information on available courses	<p>This is a responsibility of the Faculty coordinators. However, oftentimes IROs should be the first point of contact for students. They may require and to direct students to the right contacts such as the local accessibility centre, and help them navigate the new university structure.</p>
Support in preparing the application	<p>The IRO is responsible for managing the application, and processing nominations and acceptance letters.</p> <p>The IRO should be in contact with the incoming student when the nomination from partners is received.</p> <p>IROs should ensure that the student is able to join local IT services to help create university accounts and that the student is able to participate in courses.</p>
Support in finding accommodation	<p>The IRO should provide students information about available student accommodation managed by the university, or if that is not possible, guide them to some reliable sources/student groups, or warn them of possible scams. It is also important to note that accommodation provision should be prioritised for students from fewer opportunities backgrounds. Most students with health issues of students from low income families report dissatisfaction with this type of support, indicating the need for more attention in support with accommodation for these groups</p>

	<p>of students.</p> <p>Some IROs may have dedicated staff to handle dormitory applications, filling in gaps left by general student services.</p>
Support in Visa-obtention	<p>The IRO should support students in obtaining their visa. Usually, this includes justifying that the students have enough to cover living expenses, the reason for the visa (e.g., study), and may also involve helping students secure healthcare coverage.</p> <p>IRO offices should have an assigned officer working on supporting visa applications. For students who come outside of the EU, it is best to set up a buffer time for the application as it takes longer. IRO offices are encouraged to offer health insurance as part of the application for KA171 students.</p>

Accessibility & Equal Treatment centres

Support in preparing the application	<p>Accessibility centres should support students if they need to request a reasonable adjustment. The supporting centre requested may be asked about services before the arrival of the students at the HEI.</p> <p>It is highly advisable to list the services that the Accessibility Centre provides in the beginning phase of the mobility application process available on the HEI website and in multiple languages.</p>
Information about support at the host institution	<p>Accessibility centres should consult with other in-house or external partners to identify the reasonable adjustments that can be made for incoming students. In most cases, the support mechanisms already exist for their local student population. Hence, it is important that the types of support are well communicated and accessible, so that potential incoming students can make their mobility decision with certainty of the help they may receive.</p>

	<p>Common requests from students with fewer opportunities include those regarding sleeping quarters, learning aids and the accessibility of buildings.</p>
Support in finding accommodation	<p>Accessibility centres must be prepared to issue an expert opinion for students who have special accommodation needs to support them securing a room.</p> <p>They may also receive questions from incoming students on the accessibility of dormitories and buildings. Therefore it is highly advisable to create visual template descriptions of the dormitory and faculty buildings for incoming students in the native language and English.</p>
Information about funding support for students with fewer opportunities	<p>The accessibility centre may be asked for opinions regarding students who apply for additional real cost funding.</p> <p>Accessibility centres might need to support students in preparing their request for real-cost funding. Oftentimes, students are asked to make a precise calculation of the funds they need, which, given national differences, is quite challenging for students to do on their own. It is therefore recommended that accessibility centres support students in this part of the funding application.</p>

Student organisations

Information provision about mobility opportunities	<p>HEI should partner up with student organisations so that they can be involved in co-creating events, preparatory sessions, disseminate information and raising awareness in the student population about the Erasmus+ programme.</p> <p>HEIs should seek the cooperation of diverse student organisations to increase their outreach and support network. Organisations, such as the local ESN section, student parliament, faculty student organisations, clubs and others, might help them increase visibility among students.</p>
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	<p>Best practice for local organisations representing students with fewer opportunities: establish connections with the IRO office of the institution to explore how it can support their students in participating in Erasmus+ mobility.</p>
Information about support available at the host institutions	<p>Student organisations, such as ESN and those supporting students with fewer opportunities, can help students prepare for unexpected issues before they leave on mobility.</p> <p>HEIs can partner up with student organisations to organise activities that help map the available support for their members in hosting HEIs.</p>
Support in finding accommodation at the host destination	<p>Student organisations such as ESN should contribute by promoting local housing opportunities through places like Facebook group chats, WhatsApp channels and listing trustworthy housing agencies on their local website. To improve the support that they can give. IROs should support them with the content side of this information.</p>

**During
Mobility:
On-Arrival**

During Mobility: On-Arrival

Upon arrival at the host destination, incoming students will face emotional fluctuations because of the different culture and living and learning environment. In this phase, it is important for students to feel a sense of integration in the local community. For students with fewer opportunities, who can be more at risk of social exclusion, it is of essence that support mechanisms exist and are easily accessible. This is why this section goes into what HEIs can do to ensure that the on-arrival phase of the student journey is as smooth as possible and that the student participates in activities that help them enjoy the full mobility experience.

Faculty coordinators

Information and introduction about support available at host institutions	<p>Faculty coordinators must provide faculty-level information to incoming students concerning studies, information on courses, and faculty facilities.</p> <p>Faculty coordinators generally support students by providing easily accessible information about courses. They can also further improve the support for students by providing information on where the courses take place and if specific arrangements can be made (e.g. for students with special learning needs).</p>
Support with cultural adjustments and adaptation	<p>Faculty Coordinators check in with incoming students shortly after arrival, particularly when finalising the learning agreement. This typically occurs within the first one to two weeks of the academic year.</p> <p>Furthermore, it is important for faculty coordinators to have systematic check-ins with incoming students. This can be done by mail or through online calls. However, it is advisable to have in-person meetings with the incoming students.</p>
Language support	<p>Faculty Coordinators play an essential role in ensuring that incoming and outgoing students receive accurate information about language course offerings, schedules, and enrollment procedures. For incoming students, coordinators should compile and share relevant course information and may assist in navigating closed or restricted course options.</p> <p>For outgoing students, the support should continue after the</p>

	<p>departure, especially when issues arise due to timetable changes, language barriers, or the need to replace a course. Coordinators frequently mediate with host institutions to resolve such matters. This ongoing involvement demonstrates their critical role in ensuring academic continuity and successful course enrollment.</p>
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International Relations Office (Incoming Mobility)

<p>Information and introduction about support available at host institutions</p>	<p>The IRO staff should be responsible for organising the Welcome Meeting/ Orientation week. These are dedicated events for incoming mobile students. In these online or in-person welcome meetings, IROs provide all necessary information and do Q&A activities. IRO staff should also invite the accessibility office and the safety department to meet with all students, ask questions, and provide information about the support they can provide.</p> <p>Usually in the first days of mobility students feel overwhelmed and struggle with processing too much important information. It is therefore advisable that IROs prepare a more balanced schedule of info sessions, that are spread throughout the first couple of weeks, rather than the first days. It is also very important to invite diverse support structures to these info sessions. This will help incoming students accommodate to the new learning environment easily, and understand who to turn to in different situations. Various participatory formats could be considered, and organisers should aim to create a safe space where students are encouraged to interact and feel at ease to ask questions.</p> <p>This activity can be done in cooperation with a student organisation such as the local ESN section.</p>
<p>Support with cultural adjustments and adaptation</p>	<p>To better integrate students, the IROs should organise community-building events between local students and incoming students. Furthermore, within the first days, the IRO can provide the student with a welcome package of information relevant for</p>

	<p>language classes, cultural activities and festivities that will take place during their stay. For many incoming students, their codes will need to adapt. To best help them, it is advisable to inform students about specific ways that locals behave that may seem stereotypical from the outside eye.</p> <p>Regular check-ups with the students relating to their integration is advisable to do.</p>
Information about courses (schedule, enrollment)	<p>The incoming IRO may receive questions from incoming students concerning course registrations and schedules. In this case it is important to relay the information back to the faculty coordinator.</p>
Support in communication with local authorities (e.g. for registration, residence permit, etc.)	<p>The IRO staff responsible for incoming mobility should provide guidelines upon arrival to students to get their administrative papers in order. The IRO also should play an active role in helping students obtain their residency permit. This can be done by having one person in charge of supporting students with permit requirements. The incoming IRO may also organise activities such as bus tours to relevant authorities.</p>

Accessibility & Equal Treatment centres

Information and introduction about support available at host HEI	<p>The main goal of the accessibility support services centres is to create an inclusive, anti-discriminatory environment. Together with faculty coordinators and incoming IROs they should support the implementation of support strategies in place at the HEI.</p> <p>Accessibility centre staff should participate in welcoming/kick-off meetings to discuss arrangements with students who have fewer opportunities, including contact points such as phone numbers and email addresses for emergency cases.</p>
Language support	<p>Understanding that the access of information may be more difficult to receive for students with fewer opportunities. The accessibility office should be able to give guidance in several</p>

languages.

Student organisations

<p>Information and introduction about support available at host institutions</p>	<p>Student organisations, especially mobility alumni organisations such as ESN, are crucial in the beginning phase for the integration of the student into the local student community. This often happens through the moderation of group chats with incoming students where they can ask questions directly to local students and mentors.</p> <p>Local student organisations often create mentoring programmes, supported by the university, which help with accommodation, healthcare, and settling in. Student organisations often organise welcoming events, which include sharing the typical food of each student's country and trips in the host city. In cases where administrative matters come to the student organisations or mentors, they should refer back to the IRO office. Clear distinction between the roles and points of contact are necessary in order to streamline communication flow with students and understand who is at best capable of supporting them.</p>
<p>Support with cultural adjustments and adaptation</p>	<p>Local organisations such as ESN often run a buddy programme to support incoming students' social and cultural adaptation. The welcoming days also provide an excellent opportunity to learn more about the country, city and HEI, and support the initial adjustment and adaptation of incoming students.</p> <p>It is an important reminder that local student organisations in most cases rely on their own resources, which are quite limited. It is therefore recommended that HEIs support their initiatives either financially, or by providing space for activities. Providing quality support to students requires building a partnership that goes beyond financial support - the best formula is when HEIs and student organisations co-create integration activities.</p>

During Mobility

During Mobility

During the mobility, the student will be evolving from an initial adjustment toward diving deeper into the academic and social life of the local HEI. In this stage, it is important that students with fewer opportunities receive similar support that they receive in their outgoing HEI. For this to happen, communication between different departments is key to the success of the support that can be provided. Furthermore, it is important to include mentoring and language assistance programmes to help the student feel connected at all times and make them aware of their surroundings.

Faculty coordinators

Support in understanding the new learning environment	<p>Faculty coordinators are advised to have outgoing communication channels, such as teams or email, where information can be exchanged between, for instance, vice-deans and students.</p> <p>Faculty coordinators should inform students on the learning facilities such as the library, canteen and how incoming students can benefit from the full array of services that the HEI provides its local students.</p>
Support for integration in the local student community	<p>Faculty coordinators have a key role in integrating incoming students with the local faculty student population. This can be achieved by combining classes and offering English-based courses to local students, as well as by hosting faculty events and fostering interactions between local student unions and faculty-based student organisations.</p>
Support in cases of issues experience abroad	<p>Although their official responsibilities are often limited to administrative tasks, Erasmus+ Faculty Coordinators are advised to go beyond these duties to provide essential individual support to students facing issues abroad.</p> <p>They should strive not to leave students unsupported by offering guidance where possible and redirecting them to the appropriate institutional services when necessary.</p>

	<p>In more complex cases—such as health concerns or personal crises—should activate informal support networks, including personal contacts at partner universities. This hands-on, student-centered approach highlights the informal yet crucial role faculty coordinators play in ensuring student wellbeing during mobility.</p>
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International Relations Office (Outgoing Mobility)

<p>Support in case of issues experienced abroad</p>	<p>Outgoing IRO staff should prioritise doing check-ins with students while abroad. This can be done through email or survey communication and helps central office staff detect students at partner institutions that may need additional help while on Erasmus+.</p>
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International Relations Office (Incoming Mobility)

<p>Support in understanding how to navigate the new learning environment</p>	<p>The IRO should provide students with open office hours to answer additional questions about rules and procedures at the HEI.</p>
<p>Support for integration in the local HEI community</p>	<p>It is advised for the IRO staff to organise events to further familiarise the incoming students with the local students. The main goal at this stage is to improve the attitudes from local students and staff toward international students.</p>
<p>Support in cases of discrimination</p>	<p>IRO should take preventive initiatives to combat discrimination practices. Examples of such actions may include implementing a flexible format of informative and networking events focused on discrimination, such as lunch talks where the university provides food and invites guest speakers to share insights on students' rights.</p>
<p>Linguistic support</p>	<p>Language support classes should be available at the</p>

	<p>institutions. These can be used by incoming Erasmus+ students to improve their language proficiency. However, IRO staff frequently have the issue that students are admitted without sufficient language knowledge which if recurrent, should be a point of conversation in the partnership agreement between the institutions.</p>
Support in case of issues experiences during the exchange	<p>The IRO is the student's go-to-contact for resolving issues during the mobility. The support they provide should entail forwarding emails to guiding students through local systems. It is highly advisable to create a clear communication line between the IRO central level, incoming mobility level and faculty coordinator level to improve the flow of information. For this to happen, it is advisable to schedule consultation hours where students can phone or meet physically IRO staff.</p>
Support to students with fewer opportunities	<p>Support for students with fewer opportunities should be a dual process between the incoming IRO level and the faculties. The faculties should be able to accommodate special needs students and these needs should be communicated by the sending organisation or the student. IRO staff should always share the support mechanisms that already exist at the HEI, these may include help against financial, mental, discrimination hardship to students with fewer opportunities.</p>

Accessibility & Equal Treatment Centres

Support in understanding how to navigate the new learning environment	<p>The accessibility centre may receive requests from students regarding support for courses or examinations. It is advisable for HEIs to provide personal educational assistants based on the special learning needs of the student. The psychological support team should also be activated when it becomes clear that a student is struggling with their mental health.</p>
Support in cases of	<p>The accessibility centre's most important goal is to prevent</p>

discrimination or unequal treatment	<p>discriminatory practices, however, if these happen, the context and act should always be considered. There is often no tailored way of intervening. The accessibility office should hence communicate with the international office or receive notifications from them concerning cases of discrimination.</p> <p>The support that should be provided should range from discussing 1-1 with the student, involving crisis consultants, and involving other HEI units. It is therefore advisable that students are able to find information on, and be able to file a complaint in the local but also in an international language.</p>
Support in case of issues experiences during mobility	<p>The accessibility centre should provide the contact points and guide students to relevant help. In cases of serious cases such as sexual assault, the accessibility office should request the student to file a formal complaint with local authorities. In such cases, the office should inform the students about the process, inform the teachers, prevent the victim from having contact with the perpetrator of the act and provide students with guidebooks and psychological support.</p>

Student organisations

Support for integration in the local student community	<p>Local student organisations should take an active role in promoting activities to incoming Erasmus+ students with the support of the IROs. Events include visiting cities and fostering community-building among international and local students, with translators available to support those who speak local languages.</p>
Support in cases of discrimination or unequal treatment	<p>Local student organisations should have contact points of the IRO and accessibility centre for students who experience difficulties in learning due to their disability or socio-economical situation. Furthermore, it is important</p>

	<p>that HEIs ensure that local student organisations have charters that foster equal treatment.</p>
Linguistic support	<p>Local organisations such as ESN should be inclusive and have English-speaking support at standby. Moreover, local chapters can help Erasmus+ students with translating documents and make known that they provide this service.</p>
Support to students with fewer opportunities	<p>Local student organisations such as ESN should provide a mentoring programme to improve this by matching students with physical/learning disabilities together.</p> <p>The membership of the associations may support students with fewer opportunities during their stay, however if more complicated questions or situations arise they should communicate this with the local IRO office.</p>

After Mobility: Re-entry Support

After Mobility: Re-entry Support

Too often, students' reintegration into their home country environment is overlooked and can issue emotional and cultural stress. For this reason it is important for HEIs to help students reflect on their mobility abroad and connect returnees with alumni networks or career advisors to help them recognise the competences gained abroad. For students with fewer opportunities, this also means ensuring that the HEI is aware to restart reconnecting with the student to be able to give them tailored support.

Faculty coordinators

Support with re-integration in the home academic environment	Faculty coordinators should set-up strategies to help students re-integrate in their local faculty and study programme. This can be done through welcome back events hosted by local faculty student organisations and reflections exercises on the academic experience of the host HEI.
Support with recognition of period of study abroad	Erasmus+ faculty coordinators could play a key role in ensuring that students receive recognition of their period of study abroad, as outlined in the Learning Agreements and transcripts of records.
Feedback of the students	After mobility, faculty Erasmus+ coordinators are key in collecting informal feedback from returning students, which they should use to inform and guide future outgoing participants. This feedback should include practical advice about life and the studies at the host institution. Coordinators may also want to facilitate peer support by connecting students who have completed a mobility stay with those planning to go to the same destination.

International Relations Office (Outgoing Mobility)

Support with recognition of period of study abroad	IRO staff should support the recognition of some Erasmus+ activities. This can be the case for instance for the completion of internships that are a mandatory part of the curriculum. In such cases, the IRO staff informs the faculty level in advance to make certain that the internship will be recognised at the re-entry phase.
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Feedback of the student	It is highly advisable for IRO staff to send out home institution surveys to the re-entering students regarding experience. Moreover, this feedback should be reflected upon and discussed at a unit and or strategic level to improve the procedures and make Erasmus more accessible to all students.
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International Relations Office (Incoming Mobility)

Feedback of students	<p>The IRO should compile feedback from student surveys and identify recurring challenges and improve services for future incoming students.</p> <p>The feedback provided should be discussed with the outgoing IRO unit to be able to be used in future partnership negotiations as well.</p>
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Accessibility & Equal Treatment Centres

Support with re-integration in the academic environment	<p>The support of a psychologist or accessibility unit is available but in most HEIs is not considered a specific re-entry service.</p> <p>Many students who re-enter the academic environment back at the home HEI may face cultural shocks. Together with IRO officers, accessibility offices should tailor new plans to support students with fewer opportunities when they return.</p>
Supporting staff	Accessibility and equal treatment units are increasingly supporting academic and non-academic staff with local training on how to deal with students with fewer opportunities (learning or physical disability, careproviders...) or creating informational videos to the staff population on the available services in the HEI.

	<p>This is done as academic and non.academic support staff are the first line of contact with the student. It also helps students with fewer opportunities with social acceptance in the host HEI.</p>
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Student organisations

<p>Support with re-integration in the home academic environment</p>	<p>Local student organisations can invite returning students to Erasmus reintegration activities. They can invite them to join a mentoring system for incoming students, or pass their gained experience with mobility onto the next generation of exchange students by involving them in preparatory workshops for outgoing students. It is important that returning students find their place in their home institution and community and have the space to practice their new skills and express their emotions in a meaningful way.</p>
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STAGE 1: PRE-ARRIVAL

The preparation phase of Erasmus+ mobility is crucial for setting expectations and supporting all students, especially those with fewer opportunities. It includes briefings, language training, orientation, networks, and guidance from faculty, International Relations Offices, accessibility centres, and student organisations.

<p>Student Organisations</p>				
	<p>Application and Learning Agreement</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide application guidance, varying from promotion to selection depending on institutional setup. Support students in preparing and approving Learning Agreements, check course alignment and requirements for recognition upon return. 	<p>Students with fewer opportunities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Liaise with accessibility services. Gather info from partner higher education institutions about available support measures. Collaborate with students to identify special needs early. 	<p>Support at host institution</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Communicate with hosting higher education institutions. Strengthen networks through cooperation and staff exchanges. 	<p>Information about mobility opportunities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Co-create events and preparatory sessions with higher education institutions to promote Erasmus+. Collaborate with diverse student groups (ESN, student parliaments, faculty student orgs, clubs) to expand outreach. Best practice: organisations representing students with fewer opportunities connect with the IRO to support participation.
	<p>Mobility destination support</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Help students choose suitable universities, especially those with disabilities or special needs. 	<p>Housing</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Refer housing queries to the IRO Encourage students with disabilities to disclose needs so provisions can be arranged. 	<p>Peer support</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Connect outgoing students with alumni. Promote buddy systems. Encourage mentoring and peer networks. 	
<p>International Relations Officers (Outgoing)</p>	<p>Information about mobility opportunities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote Erasmus+ centrally through info sessions, guidance, and updated online resources. Collaborate with ESN, student groups, faculty coordinators, and alumni for peer-to-peer promotion and outreach. Share general and targeted information, including support for students with fewer opportunities. 	<p>Application and Learning Agreement</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> After nomination, provide info sessions/office hours for administrative queries; refer academic questions to faculty coordinators. For traineeships: inform on eligibility, support applications (e.g., mock interviews), manage processes, and liaise with employers. 	<p>Students with fewer opportunities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Share eligibility criteria proactively with all students, not only on request. Require proof (e.g., official documents, income statements, disability certificates) before granting additional support. 	<p>Support at host institution</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Help students prepare for unexpected issues before departure. Partner with higher education institutions to organise activities mapping available support at hosting institutions.
	<p>Financial guidance</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Explain national/institutional eligibility criteria. Guide students on documentation and application requirements. 	<p>Curriculum guidance</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Direct students to faculty coordinators for Learning Agreement preparation. Clarify rules, requirements and deadlines to respect. 	<p>Mobility destination support</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide updated lists of institutional agreements and destinations, especially in centralised systems. 	<p>Housing</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote housing opportunities through local ESN channels (e.g., Facebook groups, WhatsApp, websites). Share contacts of trustworthy housing agencies.
<p>International Relations Officers (Incoming)</p>	<p>Application and Learning Agreement</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Manage applications, nominations, and acceptance letters. Contact incoming students once nominated. Coordinate with IT services to create student accounts. 	<p>Curriculum guidance</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Redirect students to faculty coordinators for detailed course information. Act as the first point of contact, helping students navigate the university structure. 	<p>Housing</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide practical information about student housing options or reliable alternatives, warn against scams. In some cases, manage dormitory applications directly where student services leave gaps. Prioritise accommodation support for students with fewer opportunities. 	<p>VISA support</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assist students in the visa process (finances, purpose of stay, healthcare coverage). Assign a dedicated officer to support visa applications. Advise non-EU students to apply early, accounting for longer processing times. Include health insurance in KA171 applications.
<p>Accessibility & Equal treatment centres</p>	<p>Application and Learning Agreement</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assist students requesting reasonable adjustments. Respond to queries about services before student arrival. Ensure information on available services is published early, in multiple languages, on the higher education institution website. 	<p>Support at host institution</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Coordinate with partners to identify reasonable adjustments, often using existing local support mechanisms. Clearly communicate available support so students can make informed mobility decisions. Address common requests (e.g., housing, learning aids, building accessibility). 	<p>Housing</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Issue expert opinions to help students with special housing needs secure appropriate rooms. Answer questions on dormitory accessibility. Provide visual templates of dorms and faculty buildings in local language and English. 	<p>Students with fewer opportunities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide expert opinions for applications to additional real cost funding. Assist students in preparing detailed funding requests, especially where national differences make calculations difficult.

STAGE 2: ON ARRIVAL

Upon arrival, outgoing students often experience emotional ups and downs as they adapt to a new culture and learning environment. Feeling integrated into the local community is key—especially for students with fewer opportunities, who are at greater risk of exclusion. This section outlines how higher education institutions can support a smooth arrival phase and encourage participation in activities that enrich the mobility experience.

<p>International Relations Officers (Incoming)</p>	<p>Information about support at host institutions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organise “Welcome Meetings” or “Orientation Weeks” (online or in person), providing key information, Q&A, and introductions to support services (e.g. accessibility, safety). To avoid overload, sessions should be spread across the first weeks and include diverse formats, ideally in cooperation with student organisations. 	<p>Support with cultural adjustment and adaptation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Support integration through community-building events with local students, welcome packages with language/cultural information, and regular check-ins. Sharing local customs helps incoming students adapt more smoothly. 	<p>Courses guidance</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Answer initial questions on course registration and schedules but should redirect academic matters to faculty coordinators. 	<p>Assistance with communication with local authorities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Guide students through local registration and residence permits, ideally with a dedicated officer and practical activities (e.g. group visits to authorities).
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Faculty Coordinators

Information about support at host institutions

- Provide faculty-level information on courses, facilities, and study arrangements, including accessibility needs.
- Can enhance support by sharing details on course locations and special provisions.

Support with cultural adjustment and adaptation

- Check in with incoming students within the first weeks, often when finalising learning agreements.
- Regular follow-up, ideally in person, helps monitor adjustment.

Language support

- Ensure incoming and outgoing students access accurate information on language courses, schedules, and enrollment.
- Assist outgoing students after departure by resolving timetable issues, language barriers, or course substitutions with host institutions.

Accessibility & Equal treatment centres

Information about support at host institutions

- Work with IROs and faculty coordinators to ensure inclusive, anti-discriminatory environments and implement support strategies.
- Join orientation events to discuss arrangements with students with fewer opportunities and share key contact points.

Language support

- Provide guidance in multiple languages to ensure accessible communication.

Student Organisations

Information about support at host institutions

- Help incoming students join the local community through group chats, mentoring, and welcome events.
- Assist with accommodation, healthcare, and settling in, while referring administrative issues back to the IRO. Clear role division is essential.

Support with cultural adjustment and adaptation

- Run Buddy programmes and welcome days to support social and cultural integration.
- HEIs should back these initiatives with resources or space, fostering partnerships to co-create quality integration activities.

ROADMAP FOR INCLUSIVE MOBILITY SUPPORT

STAGE 3: DURING MOBILITY

During mobility, students transition from initial adjustment to deeper academic and social integration. For students with fewer opportunities, consistent support — mirroring that of their home institution — is essential. Effective interdepartmental communication, along with mentoring and language assistance, helps students stay connected and navigate their new environment.

<p>International Relations Officers (Outgoing)</p> <p>Support in cases of issues experienced abroad</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regularly check in with students (e.g. by email or surveys) to detect issues early and provide help when needed. 				
<p>Student Organisations</p> <p>Support for integration into the local student community</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organise community-building activities with IRO support (e.g. trips, city visits) and ensure inclusivity through translation or English-speaking support. 				
<p>Accessibility & Equal treatment centres</p>	<p>Support in understanding the new learning environment</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Offer open office hours to answer questions and provide guidance. 	<p>Support in cases of issues experienced abroad</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Act as the main contact for issues, forward queries, and maintain clear communication between central IRO, faculty coordinators, and incoming staff. 	<p>Support in cases of discrimination</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Take preventive measures, e.g. flexible format of info or networking events with guest speakers. 	<p>Support in cases of discrimination</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Maintain contact with IROs and accessibility centres. Adopt charters promoting equal treatment. <p>Language support</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Help with document translation and offer English-language support. <p>Support to students with fewer opportunities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Run mentoring/buddy programmes, provide peer support, and refer complex cases to IROs.

STAGE 4: AFTER MOBILITY

Reintegration after mobility is often overlooked, causing emotional and cultural stress. Higher education institutions should support students in reflecting on their experience, linking them with alumni or career advisors to recognise skills gained abroad. For students with fewer opportunities, tailored follow-up and renewed support are especially important.

<p>International Relations Officers (Incoming)</p> <p>Student feedback</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collect and analyse incoming student feedback to improve services and share with outgoing IROs for future partnership negotiations. 				
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International Relations Officers (Outgoing)

Support with recognition of the study period abroad

- Support recognition of Erasmus+ activities, such as mandatory internships, by coordinating with faculties in advance.

Student feedback

- Send surveys to returning students and use insights to improve processes and accessibility at institutional level.

Student Organisations

Support with reintegration into the home academic environment

- Organise “nostalgia” or reintegration events to welcome back Erasmus students into the local community.

Accessibility & Equal treatment centres

Support with reintegration into the home academic environment

- Offer psychological and tailored support for returning students, especially those with fewer opportunities.

Staff support

- Train academic and non-academic staff, or provide resources like videos, on how to assist students with disabilities or special needs. This strengthens social acceptance and awareness.

